

EARTH SCIENCES

PROCESSING GRAVITY-MAGNETIC DATA FOR FIELD SEPARATION

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Abstract

This article focuses on the basic processing of gravity-magnetic data to separate fields into regional and local components. A key stage in the processing and interpretation of gravimetric and magnetic data is the potential field transformation phase, which involves identifying local and regional anomalies from the total observed field. Local potential field anomalies reflect structural heterogeneities in the density and magnetic properties of rocks, while regional anomalies are associated with the deep structure of the Earth's crust. To perform the transformation of gravimetric and magnetic fields, the department developed an algorithm and the Force-Fortran program IZOTR, which enables digital data transformation using various transformation methods. This article describes the algorithm and block-diagram of the IZOTR program, as well as some of the results of processing actual and simulated gravity-magnetic fields using this program in a modern interface.

Keywords: gravity field, magnetic field, algorithm, transformation, local and regional anomalies, averaging method.

Introduction

Currently, both in Azerbaijan and around the world, gravimetric and magnetometric surveys are conducted using high-precision digital instruments. Digital recording of geophysical data (particularly gravimetric and magnetometric) offers a number of advantages, including high accuracy, the ability to transmit data to a computer and over long distances without distortion, and the ability to work in automated processing systems. The Department of Geophysics at the Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University has been conducting research for several years to improve the resolution of gravity and magnetic exploration during the processing and interpretation of gravity and magnetic data [1-8]. The primary goal of this research is to improve traditional methods, algorithms, and data processing programs to improve the accuracy of local anomaly detection. Furthermore, a large volume of analog and digital data has been accumulated in Azerbaijan.

An important stage in the processing and interpretation of gravimetric and magnetic data is the primary processing stage. This stage involves the transformation of potential fields to isolate local and regional

anomalies from the total observed field. Local potential field anomalies reflect structural heterogeneities in the density and magnetic properties of rocks and primarily reflect the structure of sedimentary strata. Regional anomalies, on the other hand, are associated with the deep structure of the Earth's crust, that is, the structure and shape of granite and basalt layers. Elements of mathematical statistics, along with various algorithms and computer data processing programs, are used to identify local and regional potential field anomalies. It should be noted that these formulas allow only approximate selection of transformation parameters, since objects of varying sizes can exist at the same depth.

Means and methods

To perform the transformation of gravimetric and magnetic fields, the department developed the IZOTR algorithm and program. Unlike other algorithms, this allows for the transformation of digital and analog data using various transformation methods with arbitrary transformation parameters [1, 8]. The algorithm and block diagram of the IZOTR program are described below (Fig. 1).

Fig.

1. Block-diagram of the IZOTR program

According to the IZOTR algorithm, the following parameters are entered at the beginning:

ZMAC - map scale factor (ZMAC = 1 for a scale of 1:100000, ZMAC = 2 for 1:50000, ZMAC = 4 for 1:25000, ZMAC = 0.5 for 1:200000);

LP - sign for entering $\Delta g(i, j)$ values as a map; LG - sign for entering $\Delta g(i, j)$ values by columns; LGO - sign for entering error values and their coordinates; N, M - number of rows and columns; FOR - format factor; SOCH - interpolation error level. Then, the following parameters are entered in the loop:

NTR - transformation number:

001 is the method of analytical continuation of the field into the upper space to heights Z01, Z02 and formation of their difference;

002 is the analytical continuation into the upper half-space;

003 is the calculation of the difference between the field values and the analytical continuation to the height;

004 is the analytical continuation into the lower half-space;

005 is the calculation of the difference between the field values at the earth's surface and the values analytically continued into the lower half-space;

006 is the residual Saksov-Niagard anomalies;

007 is the calculation of the regional background using the averaging method;

008 is the calculation of local anomalies using the averaging method;

009 is the calculation of the second vertical derivatives of gravity or magnetic field (using the Elkins formula);

010 is the calculation of the total horizontal gradient of gravity or magnetic field;

NRO is the number of transformation radii;

RO(1) is the value of transformation radii;

Z01, Z02 is the first and second heights for downward or upward rescaling;

NMD is the flag for reducing the map scale when printing by NMD times.

Z01, Z02 are the first and second heights of the downward or upward recalculation;

NMD is the map scale reduction factor for printing by NMD times.

The IZOTR algorithm, developed at the Geophysics Department, performs the following transformations:

1) Andreev's variations:

$$\Delta g_{loc} = \Delta g_i(0) - \frac{\Delta g_{i-1} + \Delta g_{i+1}}{2} \quad (1)$$

2) Averaging method:

$$\Delta g_{loc} = g(0) - \Delta g_{reg}, \quad (2)$$

Here $\Delta g_{per} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \Delta g(r_i)}{n}$ is the regional component of the original field; n is the number of points in the circular palette.

3) Residual anomalies R(g) Saxon-Nygard

$$R(g) = \frac{\Delta g(r_1) - \Delta g(r_2)}{r_2 - r_1} \quad (3)$$

4) Elkin's second vertical derivatives of gravity:

$$\frac{1}{60r^2} [44g(0) + 16\bar{g}(r_1) - 12\bar{g}(r_2) - 48\bar{g}(r_3)], \quad (4)$$

where $g(0)$ and $\bar{g}(r_i)$ are the value of gravity at the center of the palette and the average value over a circle with radius r_i ;

5) The total horizontal gradient of the potential field :

$$w_{sz} = \sqrt{w_{xz}^2 + w_{yz}^2}, \quad (5)$$

where w_{xz} и w_{yz} are the horizontal gradients of gravity along the x- and y-axes;

6) Analytical continuation to the upper half-space using the Poisson integral:

$$u(0,0,-z_0) = \frac{z_0}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^\infty \frac{u(r,\alpha,0)drd\alpha}{(r^2+z_0^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \quad (6)$$

Or in numerical form:

$$u(0,0,-z_0) = \sum_{i=1}^n \bar{u}(r_i, 0,0) \left(\frac{z_0}{\sqrt{z_0^2+r_i^2}} - \frac{z_0}{\sqrt{z_0^2+r_{i+1}^2}} \right), \quad (7)$$

where $\bar{u}(r_i, 0,0)$ is the average value of the field along the i-th radius;

$u(0,0,z_0)$ is the value of the field extended to the height z_0 ; $u(r,\alpha,0)$ - the value of the original field.

7) Analytical continuation to the lower half-space (according to Gauss's theorem on the mean value of a harmonic function):

$$u(0,0,-h) = 6u(0,0,0) - u(-h,0,0) - u(0,-h,0) - u(0,h,0) - u(0,0,h) - u(h,0,0), \quad (8)$$

where $u(0,0,-h)$, $u(0,0,0)$, $u(-h,0,0)$, $u(0,-h,0)$, $u(0,h,0)$, $u(0,0,h)$, $u(h,0,0)$ are the field values at points on the sphere;

8) Calculation of differences between the values of Δg , calculated by the method of analytical continuation into the upper half-space at two levels $-z_0$ и $-(z_0 + \Delta z)$, i.e. according to the formula:

$$\Delta g_{\text{нок}} = \Delta g_{z_0} - \Delta g_{z_0 + \Delta z} \quad (9)$$

Next, according the IZOTR algorithm the field values at the nodal points of the palette is interpolating and performs the corresponding transformation (NTK). Given the transformation parameters, this algorithm produces transformation maps as a printout on a computer screen, which is very convenient for the rapid analysis of the obtained results. With isotropic transformations, the selection of parameters is based on the size of local anomalies and the depth of the structures being studied [2-3].

One common method for transforming gravity-magnetic data is area averaging, which allows for the separation of local and regional components of the observed potential field.

To average the field, a circular palette is used, the radius of which depends on the depth of the survey. Typically, the radius is selected using an averaging measure:

$$\varepsilon = 2/R_h^2(1 - 1/\sqrt{1 + R_h^2}). \quad (1)$$

According to this formula, given the averaging measure, we first find the parameter R_h along the curve constructed using formula (1), and then select the transformation radius depending on the depth h of the survey. We find the averaging radius directly from a simple formula derived using the method of characteristic points:

$$R \geq h\sqrt{\sqrt[3]{k^2} - 1}, \quad (2)$$

where k is the parameter that depends on the accuracy of the identified anomaly.

We have also developed a difference transformation method for the averaging method to identify sources of depth-dependent anomalies. The essence of this method is as follows: each transform of the averaging method reflects geological information up to a certain depth in accordance with the transformation radius. Consequently, by subtracting field values from the transform with a larger averaging radius and the transform with a smaller averaging radius, it is possible to obtain geological information on the density heterogeneity of rocks between the corresponding depths [4, 5]. The averaging method is implemented in the IZOTR algorithm, which allows transformations to be performed using various methods and arbitrary parameters in the WINDOWS system [6-7].

Results and discussion

Below are some results of processing actual and model gravity-magnetic fields using the IZOTR program in a modern interface. Initially, a model was created from three homogeneous spheres with a radius of 1 km located at depths of 2 and 4 km (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Model bodies at different depths

Then, the model gravity field from these three spheres was calculated (Fig. 3). As can be seen, the total field is represented by a single horizontally elongated maximum of gravity with an intensity of 14-15 mGal. Local protrusions of gravity with an intensity of approximately 3-4 mGal are noted on the right and left.

The results of transformation using the method of averaging a circular palette with a radius of 3 km reveal three local gravity maxima with an intensity of 8.5 and 3.5 mGal (Fig. 4), which indicates the effectiveness of the transformation of potential fields.

Fig. 3. Model field V_z from three balls

Fig. 4. The result of the transformation of the model field V_z from three balls

Below are shown the results of the gravity field transformation for the eastern part of the Midle-Kura Depression using the averaging method with the IZOTR program, presented as digital maps in 2D and 3D formats (Figs. 5-7). In order to identify large local

elements of the gravity field of the area of a detailed gravimetric survey, isotropic transformations were performed using the averaging method with external radii of 20 km (with internal radii of 10 and 15 km).

Highs: 1 - Nasimkend; 3 - Sabirabad; 4 - Arabkubali; 5 - Chovranli; 6 - Jarli; 7 - Rahimli; 8 - Kurdamir; 10 - Myusly; 12 - Varhan; 14 - Muradkhanli; 17 - Agdash; 19 - Pirazi; 20 - Zardob. Lows: 2 - Saryalyar; 9 - Alpout; 11 - Mugan; 13 - Mollakend; 15 - Shakhsumi; 16 - Ujar; 18 - Ashagi-Lyakin.

Fig. 5. Map of local Δg_{20} anomalies (2D, in mGal units)

(Eastern part of the Midle-Kura Depression)
Fig. 6. Map of local Δg_{20} anomalies (3D, in mGal units)
(Eastern part of the Midle-Kura Depression)

Fig. 7. Composition of maps of local anomalies Δg_{20} 2D and 3D (Eastern part of the Middle-Kura Depression)

On the map of local anomalies Δg_{20} large local maxima of varying intensity are noted, first identified based on the prospecting survey data: Saatly-Sabirabat with an intensity of 18 mGal and dimensions of 50 x 20 km², Zardob (2.5 mGal, 14x10 km²), Muradkhanli (4 mGal, 14 x 12 km²), Myusyusli, Kurdamir (3 mGal, 6x2 km²), Rahimli (7 mGal) and Chovranli maximum (6 mGal, 10x20 km²). The nature of these maxima is explained by the uplift of igneous rocks, to which the uplifts of the Paleogene-Mesozoic sedimentary complex are confined.

In the eastern part of the Middle-Kura Depression, the IZOTR program was also used to transform the magnetic field of the Kurdamir-Rahimli area with an outer radius of 10 km (Figs. 8-9). As can be seen, the Rahimli local magnetic maximum with an intensity of approximately 80 gamm is distinguished here, which in turn consists of three protrusions with an intensity of approximately 60 gamm. In the western part of this area, a local magnetic minimum with an intensity of -40 gamm is observed. The nature of these anomalies is due to volcanogenic-sedimentary deposits of the Mesozoic depositional complex.

Fig. 8. Map of local magnetic anomalies Δg_{10} for the Kurdamir-Rahimli area (2D, in gamm units)

Fig. 9. Map of local magnetic anomalies Δg_{10} in the Kurdamir-Rahimli area (3D, in gamm units)

Conclusions:

1. Transformation is an important stage in the processing and interpretation of gravity-magnetic data, the purpose of which is to separate the complex observed field into its local and regional components. The algorithm is described and a brief block diagram of the Force-Fortran IZOTR program is presented, which performs the transformation of the gravitational and magnetic fields on a computer with optimal transformation parameters.

2. A computer-generated transformation of the gravity field of the eastern Middle-Kura Depression was performed using averaging with an outer radius of 20 km, confirming local maxima and minima of the gravity anomaly. The geological nature of the identified local anomalies was analyzed.

3. A computer-based transformation of the magnetic field of the Kurdamir-Rahimli area in the eastern part of the Middle-Kura Depression was performed using an averaging method with an outer radius of 10 km. Local maxima and minima of the magnetic field were confirmed. The geological nature of the identified magnetic anomalies was analyzed.

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